

URBAN PLANNING FEATURES OF ARCHAEOLOGICAL MONUMENTS FROM ANCIENT TIMES (THE EXAMPLE OF ANCIENT KHWAREZM)

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ABSTRACT

In this article, a brief overview is provided regarding the emergence of historical and cultural monuments in the ancient Khorezm region, including when and how they came into existence, the characteristics of urban planning, the formation of early city structures, the economic life and lifestyle of the inhabitants of these settlements, as well as their significance in our history.

Introduction section.

The importance of archaeological data in researching the historical and cultural processes that took place in ancient Uzbekistan is universally acknowledged. By the end of the 2nd millennium BC and the beginning of the 1st millennium BC, the region witnessed the processes of ancient agriculture, animal husbandry, and the specialization of agricultural economies. These processes had a significant impact on the urbanization of the region, leading to an elevation in the status of cities in societal development.

Department of methods.

According to the recognition of many researchers, the rapid development of Ancient Khorezm by the population was directly related to the waters of Amudarya and its tributaries. The frequent changes in the flow of the Amudarya at certain times had a critical impact on the lives of the agricultural population living in this area, many cities and villages were washed away by flood waters.

Results section.

The increase of water in the Sarikamish basins in Khorezm at the end of the 8th century - the beginning of the 7th century BC made it possible for various ethnic groups to migrate to Western Khorezm. As a result of the water supply of these areas, settled and semi-nomadic pastoralists settled in different areas and formed the Kuyisoi culture¹

According to B. Weinberg's long-term research, Kuyisoi culture dates back to the VIII-V centuries BC, and its inhabitants lived in semi-basements and cellars. Their economic activities consisted of animal husbandry, dry farming and crafts (metallurgy, pottery, etc.). Material cultural items belonging to the owners of this culture were found and researched in

¹ Вайнберг В.И. Этнография Турана в древности. VII век. до н.е. – VIII век. н.е. – Москва, Восточная литература. 1999. – с.20-23(360)

Kuyisoy-2, Yassikur village, Sakarchaga, Tumek-Kichijik burial mounds, Tarmkoya village and cemetery.²

In the 7th-6th centuries BC, in the north-western part of the lower reaches of the Amudarya, pastoral tribes of two different cultural and economic origins, the Saks and Kuysoys, lived and formed the Sak-Kuysoy culture on the basis of archaeological data.³

By the middle of the 1st millennium BC in the regions of Ancient Khorezm, as a result of the development of irrigated agriculture and the development of productive forces, a system of statehood began to form instead of primitive community relations. Ancient cities played an extremely important role in the formation of this system. According to the results of the research, the planning styles of the ancient cities of Khorezm - internal and external structure, protective structures, natural location, archaeological features, in many cases are similar to each other.⁴

The lower cultural layers of Kozalikir, one of the oldest city-fortresses of Khorezm, recognized by researchers already in the middle of the last century, were identified by S.P. Tolstov with the VII-VI centuries BC,⁵ And V. M. Masson, V-IV centuries BC⁶ was marked with In the latest studies, the conclusions prevail that life existed in Kozalikir throughout the VI and the first half of the V centuries BC.⁷ Also, recent studies show that the city of Hazorasp, located at the beginning of the oasis, is a contemporary monument to Kozalikir. In particular, the existence of Khumbuztepa, a pottery production center of the 6th century BC near Hazorasp, testifies to the antiquity of the old city.⁸

Kozalikir is an architectural monument of ancient Khorezm, surrounded by protective walls and having the characteristics of religious worship. According to archeological studies, a large area around it can be used for constructions. At this point, it should be noted that the construction of temples was important and considered one of the main factors in the urban planning culture of Central Asia by the 6th-5th centuries BC. Kozalikir, like other cities of Central Asia, is considered the fortified military-political and administrative center of the oasis, and is provided with developed irrigated agriculture.⁹

Discussion section.

According to research, it was assumed that it was the capital city of the semi-nomadic Apasmak tribal union in Kyzylkum. The old town of Chirikrabort is built on a 15-meter-high hill. Traces of protective structures built in different periods have been found in the area of the old city. According to its archaeological features, the site of the monument is egg-shaped (oval), surrounded by two rows of protective walls (42.6 hectares). There is a castle in the

² Вайнберг В.И. Экология приаралъя в древности и средне вековое// ЕО.Но1. 1997. – С.23-41

³ Вайнберг В.И. Памятники Куюсайской культуры. Кочевники на границах Хорезма (Труды ХАЕЕ-ХИ). – Москва, : Наука, 1979. С.29; Эгамбердийева Х. Амударё ҳавзаси худудларининг ..., Б.96-97

⁴ Эшов Б. Ўзбекистонда давлат ва маҳаллий..., Б.86

⁵ Толстов С.П. По следам древне хорезмской цивилизации. – М. – Л.: Издательство Академии наук СССР 1948. 328с.

⁶ Массон В.М. Древнеземледельческая культура Маргианы //МИА Но73. – М. –Л.: Издательство Академии наук. СССР 1959. 216 С.

⁷ Матёкубов Х.Х. Ўзбек давлатчилигининг илк босқичида Қадимги Хоразм: тар.фан.номз.дисс.автор. – Тошкент, 2012. 236.

⁸ Ўша асар.

⁹ Вишневская О.А. Рапарт Ю.А. Городише Кюзелигыр. К вопросу о раннем этапе истории Хорезма // ВДИ. 1997. Но2. – С.46-58; Эшов Б. Ўзбекистонда давлат ва ..., Б-87.

center of the old city (12.4 hectares). The fact that the monument is surrounded by a moat with a width of 40 meters and a depth of 4.5 meters indicates that special attention was paid to defense structures. Several tombs - vaults have been opened and researched in Chirikrabort, and the findings in them date back to the V-IV centuries BC.¹⁰

Based on the archaeological characteristics of the monuments in Khorezm, B.I. Weinberg conducted special studies to determine the origin of the culture of the archaic period in the oasis and the age of its objects. According to the scientist, the distribution of the first square-shaped raw bricks in these regions and the changes in the appearance of ceramics occurred due to direct contacts with Iran through the Uzboy tributary and the Caspian, and resulting in the spread of some aspects of Iranian material culture from the second quarter or middle of the 4th century BC.¹¹

According to H. Matyokubov, the research to determine the capital of the ancient state of Khorezm began to bear its results in the 80s of the last century. In particular, the first thoughts that the Aqchakhan fortress could be the capital of the Ancient Khorezm state were expressed. This old city, with a total area of more than 50 hectares, has a rectangular shape consisting of an inner and outer fortress, surrounded by separate protective walls. This ancient city has recorded wall paintings related to court ceremonies and religious beliefs, including a portrait of a ruler in royal robes with a crown on his head.¹²

Summary.

Summing up this section, it can be said that the processes of settlement on the basis of the acquisition of new lands in the Ancient Bactrian society of the VII-VI centuries BC are increasing. Old cities are developing, production farms, castles, and base fortifications are appearing around them. The importance of defensive structures increases in the construction of various buildings.

In the first half of the 1st millennium BC, Sugdiyana formed not only a political but also an ethnic and cultural unit within the Bactrian state. According to the archeological features of the old cities, i.e. similarities in construction methods, architectural art, and material culture prove the above points. Such similarities could appear on the basis of economic and cultural relations and political unity.

In the 5th-4th centuries BC, Khorezm and its neighboring areas were covered by urbanization processes. According to the archaeological features of the cities, historical and cultural oases of agriculture appeared in these regions during this period, and they were the basis of the first statehood.

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¹⁰ Неразик Е.Е. Древние города Хорезма и пути их развития (IV в.гон.е. – IV в.н.е.). // Центральная Азия. История, источники и культура, - Москва.: Восточная литература. 2005. – С.443-561.

¹¹ Матёкубов Х.Х. Ўзбек давлатчилигининг илк босқичида, 23.б

¹² Матёкубов Х.Х. Ўзбек давлатчилигининг илк босқичида, 23.б

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